

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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THE EFFECT OF A NURSE-DRIVEN PROTOCOL ON THE INCIDENCE OF ASPRIATION
PNEUMONIA IN A TERTIARY HEALTHCARE SYSTEM

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

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DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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Abstract

A nurse-driven protocol was developed and pilot tested to evaluate its effectiveness in preventing the occurrence of hospital-acquired aspiration pneumonia (AP) in a major tertiary healthcare system in Southern California. The project was divided into two distinct stages. The first stage was a methodological study that focused on the development of the protocol. The second stage involved testing via a pilot study. The Plan, Do, Study, Act Model for process improvement was utilized and both retrospective and prospective data were analyzed. A one-hundred percent sampling technique was used, and 134 patients (ages 18-95) hospitalized in the inpatient medical, surgical, critical care, and acute spinal cord injury units met protocol criteria. Patients admitted to these acute care settings with a community-acquired AP were excluded from the study. Approximately 231 registered nurses were trained. The outcome measures of interest were the frequency of AP, adherence to the protocol requirements, timeliness in initiating the protocol, AP protocol usage, and the nurses' level of knowledge. Results showed a decrease in the number of AP from seven to two comparing the same months (November, December, January, February, and March) 12 months before the implementation of the protocol to five months after protocol implementation. Implications were made for nurses' knowledge level, competency, and commitment for a systematic implementation of the APNP.

Keywords: aspiration pneumonia, hospital-acquired pneumonia, nurse-driven protocol, clinical practice guidelines

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He's never given up on me, despite having every reason to do so.

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Background

Aspiration pneumonia (AP) is a type of pneumonia often diagnosed in the elderly population and in patients who have suffered from neurological disorders (Wu, Chen, Wang, & Pinelis, 2017). It is caused by the introduction of pathogenic bacteria from the oral-pharyngeal cavity or the gastrointestinal tract into the lungs. These events lead to extended hospitalizations and poor patient outcomes. According to Maieda and Akagi (2017), 80% of pneumonia cases requiring hospitalizations are due to aspiration, and the rate also suggests that AP is the leading cause of death in patients diagnosed with pneumonia. Pneumonia is the second-leading cause of death worldwide (Mokdad et al., 2016; Jeon et al., 2019).

There are many pathways to the development of AP, and its occurrence depends heavily on the history of the patient (i.e., how it happens in head and neck cancer patients is different from how it transpires in a patient with Parkinson Disease [PD]). In AP, aspirated material typically infiltrates the lower right tracheobronchial tree because anatomically, the right main bronchus is straighter with the trachea. Regardless of its etiology, AP causes an acute inflammatory reaction within the respiratory system and subsequently causes pneumonia (O'Malley et al., 2018). AP's adverse effects are associated with significantly high morbidity and mortality rates, longer hospital stays, expensive antibiotics, laboratory studies, and the potential for mechanical ventilation (Echevarria & Schwoebel, 2012). Advanced age, functional impairments, polypharmacy, changes in the anatomy of the oropharyngeal airway, tracheostomy or endotracheal intubation, poor oral hygiene and the use of proton pump inhibitors are risk factors associated with AP (O'Malley et al., 2018).

The incidence of AP at the national level showed that over ten years, from 2002 to 2012, 406,798 patients were admitted to hospitals with AP. Of these, 79% of the AP cases (322,598)

were in patients over 65. This represented 40.7 patients per 100,000 patients admitted to hospitals. The mortality rate for this population was 20.7% (Bowerman et al., 2018; Jeon et al., 2019; Lanspa et al., 2013; Wu et al., 2017). Furthermore, the studies of Smith et al. (2006) and The Joint Commission (2006) demonstrated that 89% of patients with AP, a significant cause of morbidity and mortality, have dysphagia. Many risk factors besides age contribute to AP, including comorbidities such as PD (Troche et al., 2014), endotracheal intubation (Driver et al., 2018), head and neck surgeries for the treatment of cancer, and chemoradiotherapy (Xu et al., 2015).

Problem Statement

The project author became interested in conducting a quality improvement (QI) study through his involvement in AP discussions at a significant Veterans Administration Medical Center in Southern California. Data collected in the fiscal year 2019 showed that pneumonia was the highest in-hospital complication (Table 1). Although its local pneumonia rate was lower than the national average, the diagnosis was the highest in-hospital complication. The case reviews suggested that 10 of the 11 (90.9%) events of in-hospital acquired pneumonia cases diagnosed in the fiscal year 2019 were associated with AP and occurred predominately on the medical-surgical wards and the intensive care unit. Each AP diagnosis was verified through a radiograph and computed tomography, and a review of patient records by a panel of judges that included registered nurses and physician infection preventionists. As a result, a local decision was made to develop a task force lead by the author to address AP's prevalence and prevention within the facility.

Table 1

2019 In-Hospital Complication Rates and Event Counts in per 1000 BDC in the Project Units

In-Hospital Complications	Facility Rate	National Average	Number of Events
AP Pneumonia	0.28	0.38	11
GI Bleed	0.09	0.1	5
Sepsis	0.04	0.1	2
Central Nervous System (stroke)	0.04	0.12	2
Deep Vein Thrombosis	0.02	0.12	1

Note. BDC = Bed Days of Care

Another major incentive to study the incidence of in-hospital AP complications and develop strategies to reduce its occurrences is the cost, the patient, and the healthcare system. According to Wu et al. (2017), an AP diagnosis adds a cost of \$30,000 to the patient's hospitalization. Warren et al.'s (2019) study found a hospital-acquired AP diagnosis added \$40,000 to the total cost of hospitalization and increased the patient's length of stay in the hospital between 7-10 days.

Additionally, undiagnosed dysphagia causing AP can cost the medical institution an estimated \$4,300.00 per day per patient (Kaizen et al., 2003). The adverse effects of AP on the patient's emotional and psychological well-being are significant. Patients with AP often experience helplessness, demoralization, depression, and failure to thrive (Tecuta et al., 2015). The incidence of these adverse psychological effects ranges from 20% to 50% of patients with AP (Hays et al., 2002; Robinson et al., 2015).

Because AP is often preventable, the author sought to take on a proactive role by developing an AP nursing protocol (APNP) to guide nurses in assessing and managing patients at high risk for AP. The goal for this project focused on taking take pre-emptive actions to prevent AP before it occurred. Several nurse-driven studies have concentrated on reducing the incidence of AP due to such causal factors as poor oral hygiene. For example, Quinn and Baker (2014)

found that having an APNP for oral care decreased the rate of non-ventilator hospital-acquired pneumonia by 38.8% per 100 patient days. Their protocol also resulted in 1.72 million dollars in cost savings and reduced the LOS by 500 extra days. Higashiguchi et al. (2017) focused on a different aspect of oral care where nurses use post-mouthwash intervention (wiping plus oral nutritional supplement). Their results demonstrated a decrease in the incidence of AP. Similarly, the studies of Echevarria and Schwoebel (2012) and Warren et al. (2019) investigated risk assessment and oral care and found a decrease in AP rate.

These studies focused mainly on the effect of different types of oral care on AP. During the patient's hospitalization process, there are many other factors, which put the patient at high risk for AP, which the above studies have not investigated. This study developed a more comprehensive APNP approach evaluating different factors during the entire hospitalization process that put the patient at high risk for AP and emphasized a preemptive action to prevent APs. The APNP covers the timeframe from the patient's admission to discharge. Therefore, this QI study attempts to reduce AP incidence in critically ill hospitalized patients through the implementation of nurse-driven prevention methods.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this study was to develop a comprehensive APNP to reduce the incidence of AP in patients admitted to the critical care and intermediate medical-surgical units at a major Veterans Administration hospital. The study was planned to be conducted in two stages:

Stage 1: Development and pilot testing of the APNP and pilot. This first stage was the goal of the author's Doctor of Nursing Practice project.

Stage 2: Further refinement of the APNP with widespread implementation on a larger scale throughout the entire VA Medical Center, followed by in-depth auditing of its effectiveness in

reducing the rate of APs. The author will lead this second stage post- completion of his DNP degree.

Supporting Framework

Framing a DNP project allowed the leader to define its purpose, methods, and outcomes clearly. A supporting framework allows for a project's overall consistency to remain appropriately focused and maintain credibility throughout the improvement work (Bonnell & Smith, 2018). This section describes Plan, Do, Study, Act (PDSA) as the supporting framework during process improvement activities in a healthcare system.

Koenigsacker (2013) outlined improvement tools suggested for use in leading process improvement events in the Lean healthcare system. Lean tools are distinguished by the type of process improvement needed and include toolkits specifically derived for executive leadership, human development, new product development, quality improvement, standard work, flow and lead time, and transformation continuum. Thus, this section discusses the over-arching use of the PDSA with a specific A3 Thinking and Strategy Deployment tool to facilitate its use from problem-identification to solving an identified problem area.

Plan Do Study Act

According to Langley et al. (2009), PDSA is a problem-solving model that provides participants with explicit permission from facility leadership to be creative, take risks, and experiment in rapid succession. The process begins by the experimenters answering the specific questions that form the basis for improvement (Figure 1). The three basic questions are:

1. What, precisely, are we wanting to accomplish?
2. How will we know when an improvement has been made?
3. What are the changes we can make to gain improvement?

In PDSA cycles, problems are solved individually to prevent the process from becoming too complicated in scope.

Rother (2010) emphasized that Toyota manufacturing, for example, addressed one problem at a time so experimenters (frontline staff) could best understand the cause and effect of a single problem and subsequently better understand the process. If the initial PDSA is not successful, repetitive PDSA cycles, in rapid succession, are completed until the desired outcome is achieved. For the team to gain successes throughout the PDSA process, it is critical to have extensive planning for each of the four phases. It is also essential that executive level facility leadership is fully engaged in supporting the PDSA. Participants of a PDSA cycle must be given protected time to participate fully, and executive leadership must hold their management staff accountable for providing the resource of time. Intermittently pulling participants away from the PDSA process because of competing factors, such as staffing, degrades the PDSA process's value and may be viewed by the participants that management is not fully supported. Implementation of a PDSA event should be coached by someone well-versed in process improvement activities. A coach trained in Lean will participate and guide the team through the sequential phases of the PDSA cycle and will complete each phase sequentially.

Plan

The first step in implementing PDSA is the *plan* phase. In the planning phase of PDSA, objectives are defined, and the team gains a firm understanding of the area in need of improvement. Key stakeholders are identified, and the team identifies the most appropriate measurement tools that support data collection (Varkey & Kollengode, 2011). After the team has a firm understanding of the problem being addressed, possible solutions will be devised, and the plan to begin rapid experimentation(s) will be formulated. Clear role definitions will be

established of whom, for example, will conduct data collections, serve as team lead, and who will communicate the changes to the work unit. Without early role clarifications and sufficient data to drive decisions, the PDSA cycle should not proceed. After the team has understood the problem, defined tools for data collection and presentation, acquired adequate data to drive decision making and role clarifications, experimentation of possible solutions begins.

Do

The *do* phase is when pilot studies are conducted, data collection is ongoing, and the team learns about the unintended consequences of their actions (Varkey & Kollengode, 2011). The rapid experiments may be met with opposition from the work unit because of the stressors associated with change; therefore, the communication of why change is necessary should be well thought out before the event takes place. Equally important is sharing the results, both gains and losses, with the work unit, enhancing the staff's buy-in and better posturing the team for success. Sharing results may be accomplished by frequently updating the work unit before, during, and after each cycle, then summarizing the findings using visual management tools such as run charts, scatter plots, and graphs. Langley et al. (2009) discussed the most common ways the PDSA cycle can influence system improvement: the cycle can build knowledge, help answer critical questions, promote testing/auditing change, and plan implementation.

Study

In the PDSA cycle *study* phase, a plan will be attempted, and data gathered to test the change. During data collection, observations of both expected and unexpected outcomes are simultaneously made and recorded. If the data reveal the team's efforts either meet or exceed the intended outcomes, the team will begin to develop the following steps and formulate strategies that allow the improvement work to become hardwired through standard work development and

training. At times, the outcomes are deemed insufficient and do not meet the intended ideal state. In these cases, the team returns to the *planning* phase to develop new ideas and hypotheses to test and then follows the PDSA cycle by repeating each step.

Act

The final step in the PDSA cycle is the *act* phase. In this phase, the action is rationally based on what has been learned through the team's rapid experimentation (Langely et al., 2009). If, after the *planning* phase, the results of the experiment(s) are deemed valid and sustainable, the team then strives to establish standards of work that capture the lessons learned from the PDSA work. This phase is an exciting and celebrated time for the PDSA team and work unit stakeholders because the improvement work will have identified new and efficient processes. The work of the PDSA continues through regularly scheduled audits to ensure the changes remain viable and sustained. The PDSA cycles are time-intensive and require a great deal of commitment by leadership and stakeholders; therefore, regular essential audits are conducted for 90 days or longer depending on the speed of buy-in.

Figure 1*The Plan, Do, Study, Act Model for Quality Improvement***A3 Thinking**

A standard tool used in a Lean organization is an A3 Model (also known as A3 Problem Solving or A3 Thinking). It is a conceptual approach derived from the idea that all problem-solving steps for any issue should be summarized on a single standard A3 size (11 X 17 inches) worksheet (White & Jones, 2018) (Figure 2).

The first step in A3 Thinking is to determine the reason for action or the problem statement. The reason for action, the first action in the A3 Model, describes why an intervention is necessary. The second phase of A3 Thinking identifies the current state, and then a target state is established. The target state is essential because it drives much of what needs to become accomplished in the QI event. Next, teams determine the gaps preventing the target state from

becoming a reality. The team then documents possible solutions and begins rapid experimentation to test their possible solutions. Once the ideal state has been accomplished, A3 Thinking requires developing a completion plan for how to sustain the improvements. Finally, the group assembles one last time to provide their insights on the entire process.

Like other groups who addressed AP by protocol implementation, Jiang and Malkin (2015) used Lean methodologies and A3 Thinking to improve patients' surgical care experiences in an teaching facility's outpatient clinic. The Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and Systems (CAHPS) Surgical Care Survey was distributed to 17 surgical care patients to determine their perceptions of care delivered in the outpatient surgical clinic. The survey results were analyzed through Lean thinking, and subsequent improvement changes were made (Jiang & Malkin, 2015).

The systematic approach to problem-solving employed by the PDSA framework through A3 Thinking allowed the participants to remain structured and cohesive in their planning. In addressing the overall positive patient experience, certain modifications made to the standard work of the clinic allowed the team to realize an improvement from 57% answering "yes, definitely" to 93% immediately post-intervention ($p = <.001$), which was a statistically significant change.

Figure 2

Sample of an A3 Report

A3 Report: Project name		AMA STEPSforward
<p>Project mission statement What is the team trying to accomplish?</p>	<p>Solution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe recommendations of team Show diagram or map of new process Measurable targets to achieve within determined timeframes 	
<p>Background</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Problem background Why the problem needed to be fixed Importance of identifying solution 	<p>Implementation plan</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use a diagram if possible Who is responsible for which tasks? What resources are required? What targets have been identified? Timeline for achieving? How regularly will the improvement team connect while the change is underway? 	
<p>Original state/problem statement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use a diagram if possible Show where the problems exist with Kaizen bursts, i.e. graphic indicators of opportunities for improvement Extent of the problem (e.g., metrics or measures of success that are below target) <div style="text-align: center;">		
<p>Problem analysis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Why does the problem exist? Does asking “why?” five times help identify the root cause? What influences caused the problem? 	<p>Sustain</p> <p>Implementing a project doesn’t guarantee long-term success. How does the team plan to continue to make the improvement part of daily practice, long after the “project” as ended? Determine metrics to track, feedback loops for staff, and maintain regular A3 updates to share with the team and supporting leadership.</p>	
<p>Team</p> <p>Executive sponsor: Champion: Team lead(s): Project team: List names and departments</p>		

Source: AMA. Practice transformation series: starting lean healthcare. 2015. Copyright 2015 American Medical Association. All rights reserved.

Strategy Deployment

Following successes gained through the PDSA framework for process improvement, Strategy Deployment allows senior leadership to incorporate the new PDSA framework interventions, insights, and talents acquired to “review strategic efforts for the next year, identify how Lean improvement can accelerate and enable these efforts, set True North goals to support the strategic direction, establish the pace and pattern of improvement effort for the year to achieve these goals, and then establish a monthly review process” (Koenigsaecker, 2013, p. 85). While much of the Lean methodologies recognize that the frontline staff are the best resources available to understand workflow and identify waste, Strategy Deployment is executive

leadership's opportunity to take the PDSA framework-based experiential findings and commit resources for sustainment.

Brunsmann (2018) embraced this notion when Lean Methodology was used in an 802-bed tertiary teaching institution to optimize time-to-antibiotic administration in patients with sepsis. Through a Lean process improvement experience, a one-day rapid improvement event, all frontline pharmacy technicians, clinical pharmacists, and unit-based clinical pharmacy staff were invited to attend. They were asked to identify value and non-value-added tasks in the pharmacy workflow and devise solutions that eliminated waste associated with the timely administration of antibiotics to the septic patient (Brunsmann, 2018). As a result, by including the frontline staff in a solutions-based approach to problem-solving, the median overall turnaround time from order-entry to antibiotic administration time was reduced to 40 minutes from approximately 120 minutes. The key to practical problem-solving with sustained results in a Lean Methodology is frontline staff involvement from the beginning of problem identification.

Although opposition to Lean methodologies may arise from critical stakeholders, such as physicians, nurses, support staff and unions; Lean institutions realize early the principles that support continuous improvement and respect for people and the meaningful work they perform. Cohen (2018) confronts opponents of Lean by emphasizing that, while healthcare systems are not assembly lines, Lean theory has evolved to include human behavioral elements paired with innovation. Lean, according to Cohen (2018), "is a cultural transformation that alters how a healthcare organization operates.... [I]t demands new skills, new habits, and a new attitude throughout the organization from leadership to frontline providers" (p. 1452). A new approach to patient care through Lean methodologies can strengthen an organization's relevancy and care delivered to patients.

Review of Literature

Overview

There are many pathways to the development of AP, and its occurrence depends heavily on the history of the patient, i.e., how it occurs in head and neck cancer patients is different than how it transpires inpatient with PD. In AP, aspirated material is favored to infiltrate the lower right tracheobronchial tree because anatomically, the right main bronchus is in a straighter line with the trachea. Regardless of its etiology, AP causes an acute inflammatory reaction within the respiratory system and subsequently causes pneumonia (O'Malley et al., 2018). AP's adverse effects are associated with significantly high morbidity and mortality rates, longer hospital stays, expensive antibiotics, laboratory studies, and the potential for mechanical ventilation (Echevarria & Schwoebel, 2012). Advanced age, functional impairments, polypharmacy, changes in the anatomy of the oropharyngeal airway, tracheostomy or endotracheal intubation, poor oral hygiene and the use of proton pump inhibitors are risk factors associated with AP (O'Malley et al., 2018).

The next section of the literature review focuses on various factors, including costs associated with AP and critical components addressed in developing clinical practice guidelines for its prevention and treatment. In addition to costs associated with AP, the literature review examines disorders and conditions associated with AP, such as neurological disorder, endotracheal intubations, and head and neck cancers.

Costs Associated with Aspiration Pneumonia

Costs associated with AP must be viewed from both a financial aspect, the costs to manage the disease, and a psychosocial perspective, the patient's physical and emotional costs. Wu et al. (2017), using a longitudinal study that spanned ten years, studied 406,798 (weighted total, 1,741,517) patients admitted with AP between 2002 and 2012. The authors detailed the

financial burdens placed on patients following an acute care admission with an AP diagnosis among incident trends in-hospital mortality and hospital LOS. Between the years of 2002 and 2012, patients older than 65 years of age observed median cost increases from \$16,173 to \$30,280 for inpatient hospitalizations with AP diagnosis. A total change increase from \$17,517 to \$30,526 for patients less than 65 years of age hospitalized with a diagnosis of AP occurred during the study's timeframe (Wu et al., 2017). More recently, Warren et al. (2019) predicted the onset of hospital-acquired AP could potentially add \$40,000 to the total cost of hospitalization and add between seven and nine days to a patient's hospital stay.

The physical and emotional costs related to hospitalizations increased LOS, and the physical pain associated with AP can have devastating effects on patients. In addition to the physical pain that accompanies many respiratory diseases, the social, emotional, and spiritual pain requires providers' interventions as well. Unplanned setbacks in a patient's treatment plan can invoke feelings of helplessness, failure to thrive, depression, and demoralization. Tecuta et al. (2015) have defined *demoralization* as the feeling of helplessness, hopelessness, giving up psychologically, and personal incompetence.

In a systematic review of 15 studies conducted in the previous decade, Robinson et al. (2015) found that the prevalence of hospitalized patients' demoralization ranged from 13% to 18%. In another study, prevalence rates of patients experiencing elevated depression symptoms among the elderly were found to range between 20% and 50%. Depression and depressive symptoms in the hospitalized elderly patient can have adverse hospital outcomes, such as impaired hospital function, delayed recovery, increased LOS, and social isolation (Hart et al., 2002).

Key Components of Prevention and Treatment

The next section of the literature review focuses on AP and critical components to consider in developing clinical practice guidelines for its prevention and treatment. Much of the content is based upon Rosenfeld and Schiffman's (2009) determinations of the content and elements that clinical practice guidelines should include. The following were considerations from Rosenfeld and Schiffman (2009) to address when developing the APNP:

1. Define target condition or procedure – identify the procedures, conditions, procedures, or signs and symptoms for which the protocol will be intended.
2. Define target population or clinical presentations – specification of the type of the distinct patient population for whom the protocol will be developed.
3. Define intended audience and practice settings – specification about the intended users of the protocol and the precise clinical settings in which it will be implemented.
4. Identify interventions to consider and exclude – identify specific clinical interventions such as diagnostic tests, treatments, and preventative measures that will be developed when formalizing the protocol.
5. Identify outcomes to consider – prospectively selected, outcomes should be formulated to ensure the protocol's scope is limited and provides measures that allow for reliable evaluation of the effectiveness of the protocol.
6. Define the parameters of the review of the literature – identification of published, randomized, cohort, observational, and retrospective literature that is limited to adults and time periods (e.g., 1980 or later).

7. Working groups, assignments, and timelines – establishing specific assignments for groups and deadlines to ensure that experimentation, assessment, evaluation, and implementation are accomplished during the prescribed timeframe.
8. Key points to remember – the emphasis is placed on broad concepts and group consensus whereas, essential specifics are considered later.

Factors of interest in this project are the key characteristics of the population of interest who are most vulnerable to AP, including patients who suffer from neurological disorders, are post-endotracheal intubation, and have head and neck cancer with a mucositis diagnosis. These specific patient groups were chosen because they closely represent the patient population and demographics at the hospital where the project was implemented. Its prevalence, adverse effects on patients, and the frequency and costs associated with AP are evaluated, and existing evidence supports the implementation of an APNP to prevent AP. Because of AP's expansive patient populations, the evidence within the literature review justifies continued strategy development and interventions to address the dangerous condition of AP.

Prevalence of Aspiration Pneumonia

To describe the United States, national trends in acute care admissions for AP from 2002 to 2012, Wu et al. (2017) reviewed a total of 406,798 patients admitted to a hospital for AP. The authors evaluated the electronic health records of 84,200 (20.7%) patients who were younger than 65 years of age and 322,598 (79.3%) patients who were over 65 years of age. AP's overall incidence decreased between 2002 and 2012 from 8.2 to 7.1 cases per 10,000 patients, and in-hospital mortality decreased from 18.6 % to 9.8%. For patients older than 65, the incidence decreased from 40.7 to 30.9 cases per 10,000 patients, with a decrease in in-hospital mortality from 20.7% to 11.3%. Through multivariable logistic analysis, the age of patients, those over 65

years of age, and admission to a non-teaching hospital were found to be independent predictors of in-hospital mortality. There were certain limitations to the study disclosed by the authors:

1. The diagnosis of AP may have been provider-dependent, and the diagnosis underestimated.
2. The data only represented inpatient data and did not include outpatient data; therefore, those suffering from AP on an outpatient basis were not captured.
3. The authors pulled data that were unique to specific diagnosis coding and were subject to misclassification.

Although their study showed a decrease in AP incidence and mortality, the costs for hospitalizations doubled during the same timeframe between 2002 and 2012, and the need for mitigating AP remains a national priority (Wu et al., 2017).

Disorders and Conditions Associated with AP

Neurological Disorders

Among those most at risk of dying from AP are patients with a diagnosis of PD. According to Troche et al. (2014), AP is the leading cause of death in PD patients. In their prospective study, 20 participants (six women) with mild to moderate PD (with and without dysphagia) were enrolled in a study to test their reflex cough thresholds and urge-to-cough (UTC) ratings. Participants were asked to complete a capsaicin challenge by accepting three randomized doses of 0, 50, 100, and 200 mM capsaicin (Troche et al., 2014). Because 200 mM capsaicin is the threshold for eliciting a healthy person's cough response, *Cough Threshold* (CrTot) and *Urge to Cough* (UTC) outcome measures were recorded at that dose. The investigators conducted a regression analysis to determine when the P-A score (penetration and aspiration) (dysphagia severity) ($b = -1.359$, $p = .031$) is increased, and the CrTot is decreased.

PD severity was not a significant variable to swallowing dysfunction ($rs = 0.091, p = .704$) (Troche et al., 2014). This is important because the data suggested all patients with PD (regardless of PD Hoehn and Yahr Scale severity stage), coupled with AP being the leading cause of death in the PD population, were likely to die of AP. The age ranges, proportion of male to female, and prevalence of PD closely resemble the project hospital's demographics. Implications from this research study support consulting speech and language pathology about the need for swallow studying, which was incorporated into the author's general protocol.

Endotracheal Intubation

Another cohort of patients who remain vulnerable to AP is those requiring emergency endotracheal intubation to secure their airway. In an emergency department (ED), patients who require emergency endotracheal intubation have typically not fasted and may be suffering from a range of critical etiologies. In a 2018 prospective observational study of a large urban ED in the US, Driver et al. (2018) used a standard definition of AP to determine its incidence following endotracheal intubation. With AP as the outcome measure in their study, Driver et al. (2018) used descriptive analytics to analyze data from 823 patients for 22 months (June 2010 to November 2011 and July 2012 to November 2012).

Study results demonstrated 29% of patients developed pneumonia (238/823): 16% (134/823) developed AP before endotracheal intubation, and 8% (66/823) developed AP within 48 hours post- endotracheal intubation. Preventive measures post-endotracheal intubation is an essential management aspect as noted in the Driver et al. (2018) study as 200 patients suffered from AP post-endotracheal intubation. Furthermore, as discussed subsequently in this author's literature review, post-intubation AP can be prevented if there is an early implementation of an APNP. Specifically, the issuance of an incentive spirometer, head of the bed (HOB) at 30-45

degrees, oral care, and a proton pump inhibitor as required in the project hospital's general protocol.

Head and Neck Cancer

AP, after concurrent chemoradiotherapy in patients with head and neck cancer, is often under-reported. As reported by Xu et al. (2015), previous studies have shown rates ranging from 33% to 81%. Additional research indicates AP is a significant post-cancer treatment morbidity. Xu et al. (2015), in determining risk factors associated with AP, stratified data from head and neck cancer patients with non-cancer patients who had suffered from AP. This allowed for a comparative analysis between the two cohorts, which revealed the cumulative incidence of AP in patients with head-and-neck cancer ($n = 3513$) was 15.8% and 23.8% at one-year post-chemoradiotherapy and five-year post-chemoradiotherapy, respectively. Whereas, for non-head and neck cancer patients ($n = 3513$), their data showed a 3.6% and 8.7% AP incidence at one-year post-chemoradiotherapy and five-year post-chemoradiotherapy respectively ($p < 0.001$). The age of a patient with head and neck cancer was also suggested to be a risk factor for AP, with those being 85 years of age and older at most risk. Data on patients receiving care in a teaching hospital versus a non-teaching hospital were also examined and suggested head and neck cancer patients in a teaching facility were at more risk of developing AP (Xu et al., 2015). The researchers hypothesized the reason might be that teaching hospitals often care for sicker and more complex patients. The findings of Xu et al. have implications for the author's APNP for several reasons. The project hospital is a teaching hospital where head and neck cancer treatment is common, and the age demographic resembles that of the study facility.

Nurse-Driven AP Protocols and Implementation Considerations

Protocols, bundles, clinical pathways, and screening tools have improved standardization for the early identification and treatment of patients at risk for AP (Altman, 2011). The application of evidence-based research has improved patient outcomes by empowering nurses to practice more collaboratively and autonomously (Engvall et al., 2014). In a study by Echevarria and Schwoebel (2012), frontline staff nurses developed an AP risk assessment tool and an APNP to combat the disease's challenges. Their APNP was devised from evidence obtained through literature reviews and needs assessments utilizing the Quality Health Outcomes Model as their organizing framework. Their approach was isolated to a specific pilot unit, and their strategy was deliberate and triphasic.

Phase one of protocol implementation by Echevarria and Schwoebel (2012) was executed by a hospital-based speech therapist where one-on-one training for proper feeding methods was provided. This training consisting of proper feeding and positioning techniques included all patient-care technicians and adults from the facility's volunteer department. Education also included early detection of patients who demonstrated signs of dysphagia and aspiration. During the early evaluation phase of the QI event, the authors recognized too many patients were unnecessarily placed on the APNP. Forty-nine patients were placed on the APNP despite only 31 meeting clinical criteria; therefore, the need for ongoing assessments and further detailed admission assessments was identified (Echevarria & Schwoebel, 2012).

Phase two included additional staff education on the program's background and overview, the project objectives, and proper utilization of both the risk assessment screening tool and the APNP. The unit educator educated all unit-based professional nursing staff, and additional education was provided to other medical/surgical nurses from different units to expand

the program after successful implementation on the trial unit. Phase three of the APNP consisted of refinement and distribution of the patient education materials to patients and families (Echevarria & Schwoebel, 2012).

During the trial period, patients were assessed for aspiration based upon the risk assessment tool and, if indicators were met, they were placed on the APNP. A strength of the protocol described by Echevarria and Schwoebel (2012) was developing a functional assessment that included evaluations of the patients' ability to sustain alertness, oxygen saturations, adequate chewing abilities, a strong gag/cough reflex, and normal annunciations during oral intake. For one year, only one patient was diagnosed with hospital-acquired AP and the local supporting evidence added to the overall body of evidence supporting the use of protocols to prevent AP. The evidence and techniques presented in the Eschevarria and Schwoebel (2012) study are essential to the author's project because similarities exist. For example, the authors' protocol required the nurse to evaluate the patient's neurological and general status, such as level of consciousness, neurodegenerative diseases (PD and stroke), respiratory system, and feeding tube for enteral feedings. There was also significant emphasis placed on the importance of speech and language pathology consultations. Based on the evidence presented in this literature alongside the evidence found within the literature review, these risk factors were integrated into the protocol that the project author implemented.

In the O'Malley et al. (2018) study, Project SITUP (Screen, Identify, Test, Understand, Plan) was developed to improve oropharyngeal dysphagia (OD) screening to reduce the incidence of AP at an academic quaternary medical center in the Northeastern US. Like this QI project hospital, Southern California Veterans Affairs Healthcare System, the event was piloted on medical/surgical units with approximately 60 clinical nurses who provided acute care

interventions for patients with a myriad of healthcare diagnoses. This medical center, too, used a multidisciplinary approach to problem-solving.

A project manager, attending physicians, nurse managers, a clinical nurse specialist, and a clinical nurse leader conducted retrospective chart reviews to further understand the screening for oropharyngeal dysphagia and decrease AP's rates on their medical/surgical units. The rapid-improvement cycle, modeled through the PDSA QI methodology was utilized in Project SIT UP to find interventions to reverse the prevalence of AP quickly.

(<http://www.ihl.org/resources/Pages/HowtoImprove/default.aspx>), Outcome measures consisted of screening for protocol compliance, the median number of hours between the initiation of a speech and language pathologist consultation, the actual time the consult was completed, and actual AP rates. Through their comprehensive reviews, the team members found that most AP patients previously underwent a procedure that required sedation and had been screened through an existing screening tool. This screening tool had three components: assessment of signs and symptoms of OD, assessment of psychomotor capabilities and alertness, and administering three-ounce water swallow test. Modifications needed relating to gaps in the assessment tool were identified and corrected, and then, in July 2013, the team began the *plan* phase of the PDSA cycle. With the initial screening tool in mind, Project SITUP development was formed, and efforts to publicize the project to all stakeholders, including staff, patients, and patient's families, began (O'Malley et al., 2018). The stakeholders' education followed a train-the-trainer approach and 15 unit-based nurse champions for three units were identified and received one-on-one training by a speech and language pathologist. After the trainers were adequately educated, marketing specialists were used for creating posters, banners, and uniform swag to generate awareness and buy-in from stakeholders (O'Malley et al., 2018).

The *do* phase objective was early identification of patients most at risk of, or actively displaying, signs and symptoms of oropharyngeal dysphagia. The screening protocol was separated into three sections: Part 1: Assessment for signs and symptoms of OD, Part 2: Psychomotor/level of consciousness assessment, and Part 3: a three-oz water swallow test. The protocol was introduced into the nurses' treatment plans, and the clinical nurse specialist's coaching started immediately. The *study* phase of the PDSA cycle for implementation of Project SITUP began six months after implementing the *do* phase and consisted of a complete analysis of compliance through routine auditing of nurses' adherence to the protocol.

Data collection commenced for six months, and the outcome measures were evaluated. For the first outcome measure, screening protocol compliance, the rates ranged from 88.6% to 96.3% on all three units. The second outcome measure, the median number of hours between the initiation of a speech and language pathologist (SLP) consultation, revealed the median number of hours a patient waited for the completion of an SLP consultation was 15, and the longest waits ranged from 23.5 to 38.5 hours when there was no SLP on campus. The third outcome, AP rates, was calculated using a Mann-Whitney *U* test where AP rates for the 12 months before project implementation (12.139 cases per 1000 patients) were compared to the 12 months post-implementation (5.833 cases per 1000 patients). Successful implementation of this QI event utilizing the PDSA model for process improvement showed a statistically significant change in AP rates ($p = .046$) (O'Malley et al., 2018). The final phase of the PDSA cycle was the organization's plan to *act* on the findings of the patient outcomes.

The *act* phase began in May 2014, and the team evaluated their lessons learned from the *do* phase, and strategies for ongoing audits and sustainment began. It was identified that screening was the essential intervention in the prevention of AP. Ongoing re-education of

nursing staff, especially the unit-based champions' re-education, led to the development of a learning module on OD screening and AP prevention by the healthcare system's Nursing Education, Innovation and Professional Development Department. Additional emphasis was placed on SLP staff members' availability on weekends and unnecessarily prolonged *nothing by mouth* orders for the hospitalized patients (O'Malley et al., 2018). According to O'Malley et al. (2018), AP rates' future goals were set at, or below, 7.0 cases per 1000 patients, screening compliance goals of 90% in all three units, and expanding the Project SITUP to other acute care units.

Between 50% and 75% of patients receiving mechanical ventilation will suffer from AP. Before implementing an intervention to decrease the incidence of AP in a medical intensive care unit, Bowman et al. (2005) discovered baseline rates for hospital-associated pneumonia were 6.8 cases per 1000 patient days. The risk factors associated with a decreased level of consciousness, the need for enteral feedings or endotracheal intubation, delayed gastric emptying, and supine positioning all place the patient at a greater chance of developing aspiration pneumonia. Chart audits indicated at least two risk factors were present in 94% of the pre-implementation group ($N = 18$) and 100% in their post-implementation group ($N = 13$) (Bowman et al., 2005).

While much emphasis was placed on developing a standardized feeding protocol, the prevention of AP was the main objective of the QI event; therefore, an algorithm on methods for lowering the incidence of AP was also developed. The Bowman researchers had sought evidence-based literature on the triggers of AP and the methods used to detect aspiration. Methods, such as the blue dye method, glucose oxidase, gastric residual volumes, handling of gastric residual volumes, and the feeding tube's location, were explored. The team chose two methods that reduced the risk of aspiration, such as elevating the head of the bed and practices to

promote gastric emptying and incorporating these overarching interventions into the feeding protocol and the aspiration risk reduction algorithm. Before implementation of the feeding protocol and algorithm, the team gathered additional baseline data. The data were gathered using a nurse survey ($N = 37$) that identified attitudes and knowledge related to caring for a patient with enteral feedings and a QI monitor of chart audits that identified practice norms (Bowman et al., 2005). Data revealed opportunities for improvements in the areas of ease in the documentation of enteral feeding volumes, the elevation of the head of the bed, feeding goal rates, and residual feeding volumes (when to "hold" feedings or "advance" feedings).

Implementation of the aspiration risk reduction algorithm and feeding protocol began after a series of instructional posters, visual cues, pictorials at bedside indicating "*Heads up, feedings!*", unit resource books, and one-on-one peer instruction were completed. Multiple modifications to documentation requirements for feeding tube placement and position, head of bed position, care plans, and nutrition status were made, and an enhanced unit-based competency evaluation was also instituted. Evaluation of the effectiveness of teaching occurred between February 2004 and April 2004 by using a post-implementation survey and chart audits ($N = 13$ patient feeding days, following the same criteria pre-implementation). Pre-implementation and post-implementation chart audits demonstrated improvements in head-of-bed elevation of at least 30 degrees (pre = 2.2 times in 24 hours, post = 6.2 times in 24 hours) and mean gastric residuals for stopping or not advancing feedings (pre = 23.3 ml, post = 115 ml). The percentage of patients who attained their feeding goal rate also improved (pre = 78%, post = 85%) and the rate of feeding tube positioning appropriately documented (pre = 27%, post = 64%) was also improved. Staff attitudes, measured on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree), improved in all areas (Bowman et al., 2005). The Bowman et al. (2005)

study demonstrated evidence that the formulation of an evidence-based feeding protocol and an aspiration risk-reduction algorithm is an aggressive and effective means of improving nurses' knowledge of caring for endotracheal intubated patients at risk for aspiration pneumonia. There were many correlations between the Bowman et al. (2015) protocol and the author's protocol, such as HOB elevation, tube feeding management, and neurological assessments required in the author's APNP.

Oral mucositis is a painful inflammatory process that attacks the epithelial mucous membranes of the oral cavity and subsequently causes ulcerations that impair food intake and is likely the most dangerous non-hematological complication in the treatment of cancer (Cawley & Benson, 2005; Chaveli-Lopez & Bagan-Sebastian, 2016; Kartin et al., 2014). Mucositis occurs in 40% of patients who have undergone standard doses of chemotherapy and up to 100% of patients who have received high-dose chemotherapy or combination chemotherapy and radiation (chemoradiation, i.e., doses greater than 5,000 cGy) for head and neck cancer – incurring up to 52% higher hospitalization costs (Cawley & Benson, 2005; Eilers et al., 2014; Milazzo-Kiedaisch et al., 2016). The toxic effects of chemoradiation (i.e., mucositis, dysphagia, and mucosal atrophy) place the patient at increased risk of mucositis and AP (Guy & Smith, 2009). Thus, according to Cawley and Benson (2005), the cornerstone to preventing and minimizing infection impacts is an oral-care nurse-driven protocol. Although there is no single evidence-based nurse-driven protocol that is more effective than another, it is well-known that patients suffering from oral mucositis benefit from regular mouth care efficacy. Such treatments include frequent oral hygiene, prophylactic mouth rinses, and routine oral assessments to detect mucositis (Cawley & Benson, 2005; Eilers et al., 2014).

In an evidence-based QI project, Warren et al. (2019) sought to implement an oral care protocol in adult inpatient care areas and evaluate the impact on preventing hospital-acquired pneumonia. The authors conducted a retrospective chart review utilizing the ICD 9 and ICD 10 codes to collect baseline incidence data for patients diagnosed with pneumonia not present on admission. Outcome variables included hospital-acquired cases of pneumonia, non-ventilator hospital-acquired pneumonia, and ventilator-associated pneumonia; data were collected in two seven-month periods – at baseline and intervention. To control seasonal differences in pneumonia diagnoses, the two seven-month periods were over the same seven months in two concurrent years (Warren et al., 2019). Lastly, evaluations of oral care interventions were compared using data from oral care supply use to measure adherence in the intervention group. The need for a practice change was identified based upon baseline data analysis and the make-up of the inadequate oral care kits, which lacked vital components, such as baking soda and suction toothbrushes for at-risk patients and packaging that did not promote ease-of-use. The need for a standardized protocol that guided on the level of oral care required for patients was determined to be a necessary intervention in combatting their unacceptable rate of hospital-acquired cases of pneumonia. As such, changes to practice included modifications to oral care kits, such as ergonomically appropriate toothbrushes with higher-quality bristles, baking soda kinds of toothpaste, alcohol-free mouth rinses, and oral swabs were implemented.

In their measurements of intervention efficacy, Warren et al. (2019) identified a baseline patient population of 202 and compared their data to that of the intervention group of 215 patients. Post-intervention, a χ^2 analysis of non-ventilator pneumonia incidence indicated a significant decrease from 52 in the baseline group and 26 in the intervention group ($\chi^2= 12.8$, $df = 1$, $p < 0.001$). Deaths of patients with non-ventilated associated cases of pneumonia also

decreased from 20 in the baseline group to four in the intervention group ($\chi^2 = 4.33$, $df = 1$, $p < 0.001$) (Warren et al., 2019). These outcomes signify the essentials of a rigorous nurse-driven oral-care protocol in the prevention and management of hospital-acquired cases of pneumonia. The findings of Warren et al. (2019) provide significant insight into how nurses prospectively take an active role in the prevention of AP through a more standardized approach to providing oral care to patients.

It is not enough, however, to have an APNP to decrease the occurrence of AP. As studies have shown, if there is no clear standard in QI evaluation or consistency in following the APNP, the results will not be optimum for reducing AP (Durant, 2017; Jordan & Moore, 2019). In a 2017 systematic review of the literature, Durant (2017) sought to discover the effectiveness of nurse-driven protocols on the clinical outcomes and prevalence of catheter-associated urinary tract infections (CAUTI). In the review, a quality assessment tool revealed a high level of bias that resulted in an average of 4.9 out of 11 quality indicators. Additionally, many project improvement activities were carried out on a single unit, which diminishes QI rigor due to participant homogeneity (Durant, 2017).

Summary

The literature review identified patients at risk for AP and suggested the implementation of an evidenced-based APNP can be an effective tool in decreasing the incidence of AP. The literature also demonstrated that proactive interventions, such as patient positioning, oral care, safe feeding techniques, and triggers on when to consult with specialists, must be incorporated into the guidelines, consistently implemented as specified in educational training, and with planned reliability audits to confirm adherence to the protocol. The purpose of this program improvement project was to provide meaningful, measurable, and translatable evidence that can

be converted into best practices to decrease the incidence of AP across varied patient populations in a VA setting. The literature review conducted for this project provided the necessary research evidence to support the development of an evidence-based protocol by a panel of professional experts in health care and supported by key facility stakeholders to reduce the incidence of AP. This was accomplished by defining the project's scope, the target condition, and the intended patient population and clinical presentation. Through the evidence obtained in the literature review, interventions such as medication, interdisciplinary consultation, patient positioning, and enteral feeding management were determined as key to reducing AP (Rosenfeld & Schiffman, 2010). The APNP developed for this project addressed critical components necessary for inclusion in the protocol guidelines and an evaluation component to analyze its effectiveness. The project design considers the project process and procedural issues noted in the literature that is essential to assure trustworthiness and reliability throughout all phases of the PDSA cycle employed for this project.

Methods

The literature review supports APNPs that contain key interventions, such as HOB elevation, comprehensive oral care, routine enteral feeding tube placement verifications, and swallow screening, in the prevention of AP. This DNP project aimed to develop a comprehensive APNP and evaluate its implementation in a critical care and medical-surgical acute-care setting of a prominent quaternary veteran's hospital in Southern California. The project was executed in two phases. The first phase consisted of the *Plan-Do* steps of the PDSA framework. It entailed the development of the APNP and the nurses' training and the development of the measuring tool. The implementation for the APNP was pilot tested in the selected hospital units and evaluated over a five-month period.

Design

This QI project applied the PDSA framework to plan, develop, implement, and evaluate an APNP. The project was divided into two distinct stages. The design for the first stage was a methodological study. It focused on the development of the APNP tool and testing it via a pilot study. Educational training took place during the first stage in preparation to conduct the pilot study. The variables investigated for stage one of the study were as follows: the dependent variable was the frequency of AP, and the independent variable was the implementation of the APNP. The two intervening variables were the validity of the APNP and the accuracy in implementing its various steps and the nurses' level of knowledge of the APNP. The intervening variables were controlled by ensuring that a panel of judges evaluating the APNP would agree at the 95% level that the content and the steps of the APNP were evidence-based, accurately adhered to, and sequenced correctly. The nurses' level of knowledge was assured by the project's special training session of nurses in the content and steps of the APNP. The application

of their level of knowledge was evaluated by two trained experts observing the nurses' performance when implementing the APNP. The trained experts also participated in the inter-observer reliability using an observation checklist. The content area was tested by a short paper and a pencil test that drew upon the nurse knowledge about AP's causes and how to prevent it. The pilot study consisted of collecting baseline data on the frequency of AP over 151 days during the same intervention months one year earlier and 151 days after the initiation of the APNP.

Participants

The medical records of all patients admitted to the designated project units were reviewed for selection as subjects for the author's APNP project. Inclusion criteria included acutely ill US military veteran patients who were admitted as inpatients into the critical care and medical-surgical nursing units at the project hospital and patients admitted from the project hospital's inpatient acute spinal cord injury center, including those who had acute or chronic tracheostomies; and had an admitting diagnosis of dementia, diabetes mellitus, head and neck cancer, post-procedural sedation, post-extubation, and cerebrovascular accident.

The exclusion criteria included those patients who were admitted with a community-acquired AP diagnosis. The participants for the implementation of the study were selected through chart reviews of all patients admitted to the project units who met the selection criteria. The number of patients eligible for the APNP was $N = 134$ with ages ranging from 18 through 95.

All acute care hospital nurses completed the APNP training module. The original design was for a group training session of all acute care RNs; however, due to the constraints relating to COVID-19 and social distancing, this was not possible. Before initiating the study's prospective

stage, all nurses who were a part of the study attended a two-hour virtual lecture on the anatomy, physiology, and pathophysiology of AP. The knowledge content area included the signs and symptoms of AP and the nurse's role in the prevention and treatment of AP as outlined in the APNP. Nurses were taught the proper use of the APNP protocol by a panel of experts. Once the nurses were certified that they were competent in both the scientific knowledge base and the use of the protocol, they were assigned to the specific patient care units where the APNP was implemented. They took part in data collection during the prospective stage of the study. In place of in-person group training, the training sessions were conducted utilizing the Zoom platform of instruction. The level of knowledge was assessed utilizing software that automatically collated raw scores. Following the training, all nurses demonstrated mastery of the APNP.

Setting

The APNP was developed for one of the largest quaternary Veterans Affairs (VA) healthcare systems in the US. Full accreditation had previously been granted to the facility by the Commission on Accreditation of Rehabilitation Facilities and The Joint Commission. At the time of the project, this veteran's health care system had over 56,000 unique patients enrolled in their healthcare plan. Of the enrolled patients, 4,000 were women, and 6,733 were deployed to support the wars in Iraq and Afghanistan. The workforce employed approximately 3,100 full-time employees, including approximately 750 full-time registered nurses (82% were minimally academically prepared at the baccalaureate degree level). The facility was also home to the largest acute care and long-term care spinal cord injury center in the US. For four years, through full-time on-site coaching from a Lean consulting firm, the project hospital had conducted many structured QI events to improve the quality, outcomes, and satisfaction of their stakeholders.

This QI project took place on a critical care unit and five medical-surgical units within the project hospital. The total number of beds on the five units was 195, and approximately 213 registered nurses were assigned to the units. In the critical care unit, nurses cared for patients who are often ventilated, sedated, receiving enteral feedings, and chemically sedated. The nurses on the medical-surgical units provided complex interventions to patients with cancer, cardiovascular diseases, systemic infections, renal and liver disorders, and diabetes. Each of the five medical-surgical units had a full time Master's-prepared nurse educator and manager.

Ethical Concerns

The author obtained institutional review board (IRB) determination for the EBP QI project at California State University at Long Beach and the project hospital. A letter of approval was obtained from the project hospital's administrative and clinical executives (Appendix A).

Measuring Instruments

The following four measuring instruments were used:

1. AP Verification Checklist
2. Patient Demographic Data Tool (Appendix B)
3. Observation Checklist: Nurse level of knowledge (LOK) and performance in executing the APNP (Appendix C)
4. APNP Intervention Protocol Evaluation Checklist

These tools are described concerning rationale, specifications of the tools, scoring, and psychometric properties in the following sections.

Validation of the Incidence of Aspiration Pneumonia Checklist

Verification and incidence reporting of AP were obtained from patient chart reviews by the trained project author. A medical diagnosis of an AP event was the appropriate source for

documenting a patient's AP diagnosis. Through patient chart reviews, the incidence of AP was recorded 151 days before (November and December 2019 and January, February, and March 2020) and 151 days after the initiation of the APNP. Patients who developed AP and those who did not develop AP pneumonia for the period were recorded. AP data were obtained from the patient's admission date to discharge. Baseline data were collected retrospectively from the chart reviews of patients admitted to the specified units over the designated 151 days. Post-intervention AP data were collected prospectively from actual patient records reviewed during the 151 days after implementing the APNP. Each incidence of AP was counted as one entry.

Data were recorded on a run chart and updated daily at the process control board before the daily meetings. The reliability of the AP data was obtained based on a double-entry method demonstrated in the chart review. For example, a doctor's medical diagnosis was one entry and the second entry was a radiographic report. Content validity of the AP diagnosis was confirmed by comparison with medical literature criteria for AP diagnosis (Bowerman, Zhang, & Waite, 2018; Jeon et al., 2019).

A panel of five judges, who were advanced practice nurses with a minimum of Master of Science in Nursing degree, reviewed both the chest X-ray report and conducted a separate reading of the patient's chest X-ray. Their agreement at the 95% level of the patient's chest X-ray findings was used as a valid measure and confirmation of an AP diagnosis.

Patient Demographic Data

The following demographic data were collected on the post-intervention patients who developed AP to determine the characteristics related to their AP and the other variables of interest: Age, gender, marital status, education level, racial/ethnic background, any comorbidities such as diabetes, hypertension, and previous oropharyngeal surgeries, medical diagnosis, length

of stay in the hospital, type of diet prescribed, the meal period when the aspiration occurred (breakfast, lunch or dinner or morning or afternoon snack time), and previous history of AP. According to the literature (Bowman et al., 2005; Echivarra & Schwoebel, 2011; Jeon et al., 2019; Troche et al., 2014; Xu et al., 2015), the majority of these demographic variables are risk factors or events around which AP occurs. It was essential to determine if these extraneous demographic variables based on findings of prior AP studies were associated with AP events during this project. The same panel of the five advanced practice judges evaluated each of the various parts of the tool for relevancy based on their expertise in identifying at-risk patients for AP and its treatment. There was consensus that the APNP contained all essential components.

Nurses Level of Knowledge about Aspiration

Two methods tested the nurses' level of knowledge: completing a cognitive test evaluating the nurse's knowledge of AP test; and knowledge about the use of APNP.

Cognitive Test: Nurse Knowledge of Aspiration Pneumonia

A paper and pencil test was used to ascertain the nurse's level of scientific knowledge of AP related to its prevention and to performing appropriate interventions during an accidental aspiration by a patient. Ten objective multiple-choice questions measured the following areas:

1. Food swallowing mechanism anatomy and physiology
2. Pathophysiology and the causes of aspiration and aspiration pneumonia
3. Preliminary aspiration signs and symptoms
4. Aspiration prevention
5. Aspiration treatment and management

The five areas had two questions each to ascertain knowledge. Since there were five areas, and each had two questions, scores ranged from zero to 10. A score of 8 (80% competency level) was

required for a nurse to be considered knowledgeable about AP. The tool content validity was established through agreement or consistency with literature (Bowman et al., 2005; Echivarra & Schwoebel, 2011; Jeon et al., 2019; Troche et al., 2014; Xu et al., 2015), and through the agreement of the same panel of five expert judges who validated the APNP. The percent of agreement between the judges was 95% or above. The reliability of the test was established via the test/retest method. Ten nurses who had completed the training process were tested twice using the same test two weeks apart. The percent agreement between the two tests was 100%.

Knowledge and Competency Following the Aspiration Pneumonia Nurse Protocol (APNP)

The APNP consisted of step-by-step specifications of all actions that the nursing personnel would perform in the care of acutely ill patients to prevent AP. The APNP instrument consisted of eight areas of daily patient assessments from admission to discharge that included the following critical elements of assessments and interventions:

1. Medical diagnosis: Medical diagnoses consisted of eight categories of diagnoses/medical conditions considered high-risk indicators for AP. They included a history of dementia, CVA, post-extubation, post-procedural sedation, history of head and neck cancer, history of diabetes mellitus, cerebrovascular accident, neurologic disorders, and dysphagia.
2. Speech pathology consultation: An automatic speech and language pathology consult was initiated by the nurses when they met the APNP inclusion criteria. The consult was to be completed within 24 hours of admission.
3. Presence of feeding tube: Five areas of assessment included the following: elevation of the head of the bed 30-45 degrees, verification of feeding tube placement, proper anchoring of feeding tube, checking for gastric residuals, and performance of oral care.

4. Feeding assessment (no feeding tube): Five areas of assessment that included the following: head of bed 30-45 degrees, swallow test, assessment of alertness concerning person, place, and time, assessment of oxygen saturation, assessment of chewing ability, checking for strong gag/cough reflex, assessment of proper annunciation during oral intake, and oral care.
5. Post-general anesthesia inducement/post-operative: Four major assessment areas included level of alertness, presence of enteral feeding, delayed gastric emptying, and head of the bed elevation 30-45 degrees.
6. Implementation: Six critical elements that consisted of HOB at 30-45 degrees, use of the incentive spirometer according to hospital policy, daily use of the APNP comprehensive oral care plan, obtaining an order for a proton pump inhibitor (when applicable), assisting with feeding, and providing a pneumonia vaccination (when applicable).
7. Patient observation during the critical periods of post-admission and mealtimes: Eight critical areas of assessments that included elevation of HOB 30 – 45 degrees, swallowing testing, assessment of alertness, assessment of oxygen saturation, assessment of chewing ability, assessment of gag and cough reflexes, assessment of annunciation during oral intake, and providing oral care before and after oral intake.
8. Sleep time assessment and intervention: Three critical areas of assessment included elevation of HOB, assessment for alertness, and call light within reach.

Procedure

Before collecting data, permission was obtained from the university's and the project hospital's institutional review board (Appendices D & E).

Retrospective Stage of the Study: Data Collection

Baseline data on the incidence of AP in 2018 through October 2020 was collected to investigate trends in the rate of AP at the project facility. Admission data during this same time frame were also collected for pre- and post-intervention comparison as a potential intervening variable.

Prospective Stage of the Study: Pilot Study

When a patient was admitted to any of the selected clinical unit floors, the trained RN reviewed the patient's chart and determined if they met the inclusion criteria. If yes, then the nurse approached the patient and explained the purpose of the project. The nurse then collected the data beginning with admission and continuing through discharge. The nurse trained on the protocol visited and observed the patient during every meal, snack time, and bedtime.

Throughout the day, the nurse visited the patient every two hours and as necessary. The APNP protocol was used daily as a guide to ensure data fidelity best. The protocol checklist was used at every meal, snack and bedtime daily. Any observation of aspiration was intervened and recorded on the AP checklist. The trained nurse also completed the demographic data tool using information from the patient's chart. When the patient was ready for discharge, the trained nurse recorded the length of hospital stay on the demographic datasheet.

Data Analysis

Descriptive analysis of frequencies and percentages were used to report data on the demographics, including data on the number of admissions, length of stay in the hospital, types of comorbidities, and aspiration pneumonia incidences. Additionally, a paired t-test was used to compare the means of incidences of aspiration pneumonia between the retrospective and prospective periods.

Results

The purpose of this study was to develop and evaluate the effectiveness of a comprehensive APNP to reduce the incidence of AP in patients admitted to a major tertiary Veterans Administration hospital in Southern California. Both retrospective and prospective data on the incidence of hospital-acquired AP were collected to establish baseline data (retrospective) and determine the effectiveness of the APNP (prospective). Information about the number of admissions into patient care units of interest was collected to compare pre-and post-intervention admission rates. Data on demographics of patients with hospital-acquired AP, nurses' AP knowledge level, and nursing compliance (reliability) in implementing the APNP were also collected and analyzed. Patient characteristics related to their high-risk comorbidities for AP were identified in the baseline sample of patients in the high-risk population. Based upon the literature review, the high-risk AP categories evaluated during this DNP project were neurological disorders, recent intubation, history of head and neck cancer, and oral mucositis.

The years observed were calendar years 2018, 2019, 2020 and the months of January, February, and March 2021. This period was necessary as the project author selected the months of November through March for data collection, which encompasses two different calendar years; however, analyses and observations were specific to the timeframes from November through March of each year.

Results are presented in the order of nurses' level of AP knowledge; nurses' training on the use of the protocol and implementation of and consistency in the APNP use; and the incidence of AP and hospital admissions pre-and-post-APNP intervention.

Nurses Knowledge of Aspiration Pneumonia

Eighty-two percent of the nurses at the project hospital were minimally prepared at the baccalaureate level. The knowledge test consisted of 10 questions about the AP's anatomy and physiology and pathophysiology, precipitating factors, comorbidities, and prevention techniques. No demographic data were collected on the nurses who cared for patients under the APNP. A total of 231 nurses were involved in the protocol intervention/training, and one-on-one training was provided, when needed, to nurses who needed extra time to master the skills. Of the 231 nurses who participated in the project, 213 (92.2%) had a minimum of a baccalaureate degree. Eleven nurses were eventually trained outside of the original training session due to unexpected absences. Each of the 11 nurses trained passed their knowledge test on their first attempt. As a result, there was a 100% pass rate attained among the nurses.

Nurse Protocol Training: Implementation of and Consistency in the Use of the APNP

Chart reviews were conducted by the project author to evaluate the protocol implementation and adherence and consisted of a minimum of three examinations of randomly selected charts per month for a total of 15 chart reviews. The author sought to ensure the protocol had been fully implemented within 24 hours of the patients' admission to the acute care setting. The appropriateness in patient selection, adherence to the protocol's implementation, and timeliness in initiating the protocol were evaluated. The values were 98% appropriateness (patient inclusion criteria), 100% protocol adherence, and 97.3% timelines in the execution of the APNP. Retraining of the nurses whose interventions were outside the protocol appropriateness parameters or who did not adhere to protocol standards was conducted immediately after the month's audit.

During the five months of post-intervention data collection, 134 patients met the project's inclusion criteria, with an average daily census of 188. In total, three patients were not correctly identified for the protocol implementation on admission. Of the three who were not selected initially for inclusion in the study, one patient was identified within 24 hours, and two were subsequently identified beyond 24-hours after admission. Two patients in the project units had a diagnosis of hospital-acquired AP during the intervention timeframe.

Incidence of Aspiration Pneumonia and Hospital Admissions

A paired t-test was performed to compare the rates of aspiration pneumonia in the facility from November 2019 – March 2020, to November 2020 – March 2021, to determine if there was a significant difference in aspiration pneumonia events after the APNP intervention. A calculated t-value of 1.41 was obtained. When comparing our calculated t-value to a t-distribution table considering the degrees of freedom given the sample size, it was determined that there was no statistically significant difference after the intervention based on an alpha value of 0.05. In addition, 95% confidence intervals were determined from the mean and standard deviation from pre-and post-intervention groups, which show overlap (Table 2).

Table 2

Comparison of Mean AP Events Between Retrospective Data (pre-intervention) and Prospective Data (post-intervention) Using the Paired t-test

Group	Months N	Mean (SD)	t-value	p-value
Pre-Intervention	5	1.49 (+/-1.3)	1.41	0.23
Post-Intervention	5	0.4 (+/-0.5)		

An analysis of the number of admissions into acute care units was completed to evaluate if the number of patients admitted during the timeframe would allow for generalizability and

dissemination. Figure 3 demonstrates November to March admissions to the units of the project settings. It demonstrated the units' admissions were greater than 500 hospital admissions when combined between the acute care units each year. Figure 4 compares hospital-acquired AP diagnoses based on project unit incidence to the corresponding intervention months and those one year earlier. The critical care unit had two incidences of AP post-intervention. Pre-intervention data demonstrated three cases in both the medical-surgical and critical care units and one case in the acute spinal cord injury unit. Figure 5 illustrates AP's incidence from January 2018 to March 2021 and notes the November 1, 2020 launch of the APNP.

Figure 3

Running Total of Admission from November 2018 Through March 2021

Figure 4

AP Events by Hospital Unit: Baseline and Post-Intervention During Similar Timeframe

Note. ★= No AP

Figure 5

Aspiration Pneumonia Incidents 2018 Through March 202

Note. ★= No AP

As illustrated in Figure 5, in the calendar year 2018, there were 18 confirmed AP diagnoses; in 2019, 11 confirmed AP diagnoses; in 2020, the project hospital had 11 patients who were diagnosed with hospital-acquired aspiration pneumonia (one of the 11 patients diagnosed with AP occurred in November 2020, the first-month post-intervention). Figure 6 compares the hospital setting's AP incidence over the five designated month for the last three years using a bar graph format. A downward monthly trend upon the implementation of the protocol was noted except for January that had one AP case in 2021 and none in 2020

Figure 6

Aspiration Pneumonia Incidence in the Months of November, December, January, February, and March for 2018-19, 2019-20, and 2020-21

Note. ★= No AP

A retrospective chart review of the incidence of AP in the calendar year 2020 showed 36.4% of the APNP subjects had recent intubation because of either a surgical procedure or need for emergent airway support ($n = 4$), 27.3% had Parkinson Disease ($n = 3$), 18.2% suffered from head and neck cancer ($n = 2$), and 18.2% had acute mucositis ($n = 2$) (see Fig. 7).

Figure 7

Aspiration Pneumonia Incidence by Comorbidity and Average Length of Patient Stay – Retrospective Review

Reliability of the Aspiration Pneumonia Diagnosis

In a review of baseline hospital-acquired AP diagnoses, there was 100% agreement by the five experts in concurrence with the AP's radiographic report. In a separate review of the chest radiograph and computed tomography by infection prevention registered nurses and physician infection preventionists, there was 100% agreement that the evidence of AP was present.

Patients Diagnosed with Hospital-Acquired Aspiration Pneumonia Post-Intervention

The data were collected from November 2020 through March 2021. There were 134 patients with ages ranging from 18 through 95 who met the protocol's eligibility criteria. Two of the 134 on the protocol developed AP. One of these two patients who experienced AP event did not meet protocol eligibility but was placed on the APNP by the admitting nurse because of concerns that the patient was "at-risk" for AP.

Among the project hospital's five units where AP data were collected, the average daily census in the calendar year 2020 was 188 on the project units. During the post-intervention timeframe, the calculated percentage for patients with AP on protocol was 1.1% ($n = 2$) per average daily census for the five intervention months. During the corresponding five months (2019-2020), the incidence of AP was seven with an average daily census of 190. The calculated percentage for AP per average daily census (November 2019 through March 2020) was 3.7%.

Chart Audit of the APNP Patients with Aspiration Pneumonia and their Characteristics

During the study period, there were two patients who developed AP post-intervention. The expert panel members validated the diagnoses through ICD code validation, a comprehensive review of radiography images, and the images gained from computed tomography. The first patient was a 91-year-old African American male with a primary medical history significant for multiple myeloma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, congestive heart failure, chronic kidney disease stage three, and pulmonary embolism. The patient presented to the project hospital on November 17, 2020, with complaints of shortness of breath, right leg swelling, and cough with productive sputum for two days. Upon admission to one of the project hospital's acute care settings, the patient was a poor historian with generalized weakness and moderate physical wasting. Although the patient did not meet any of the project's inclusion

criteria, the admitting nurse was concerned about his risk for AP and placed a speech and language pathology consult for a bedside swallow study. The patient failed the swallow study and was then placed on the APNP by the nurse.

His diet was ordered as soft and one-to-one feeding during all meals was ordered and adhered to by the staff. Based upon the patient's chart audit, all components of the APNP were followed; however, the patient had a coughing episode during the morning meal that was determined to be due to aspiration of a small portion of his meal. Although the patient was placed on antibiotics, he still developed a fever with mild shortness of breath. His arterial oxygen saturation was essentially unchanged but was subsequently diagnosed as having AP, and he was discharged to home with his caregiver on February 22, 2021. The AP diagnosis was not the leading cause of his prolonged hospitalization but was determined to be other comorbidities such as CHF and chronic kidney disease. The care managers conducted routine follow-up visits with the patient via telemedicine, and the patient recovered from the aspiration pneumonia without apparent AP sequelae.

The second patient was a 63-year-old Asian male admitted for shortness of breath on January 4, 2021, with a low ejection fraction, a chronic condition. The patient had many comorbidities, including diabetes mellitus, coronary artery disease, congestive heart failure, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, and an anoxic brain injury resulting from a cardiac arrest that required advanced cardiac life support. Also noteworthy for this patient was a prior June 13, 2020, COVID-19 diagnosis, for which the patient partially recovered.

At that time, the patient was receiving and tolerating enteral feedings through a nasogastric tube. The medical goals were to relieve/reduce the symptoms and provide end-of-life care allowing him to have a quality end of life. The chest radiograph upon his new admission

was negative for any type of pneumonia. Adherence to the APNP was validated through routine chart audits after each shift by the charge nurse, and 100% adherence to the APNP was achieved. Through nursing documentation, it was noted that the patient's gastric residuals were within the acceptable ranges. The patient experienced a choking spell during his nasogastric tube feeding and was subsequently diagnosed on January 6, 2021, with AP and died on January 13, 2021.

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to develop and evaluate the effectiveness of a nurse-driven comprehensive APNP to reduce the incidence of AP in patients admitted to a major tertiary Veterans Administration hospital in Southern California. Results are discussed in the order of nurses' level of knowledge of AP, educational training about the protocol, and findings on the incidence of AP post-intervention compared to the retrospective study. Implications of the study, its limitations, and suggestions for future studies are also addressed.

Nurses' Level of Knowledge

The nurses responsible for implementing an APNP must be knowledgeable of the anatomy and pathophysiology of AP. This allowed the nurses to identify precipitating factors and prevent the onset of AP quickly. Pre- and posttesting support that the nurses participating in this project achieved essential knowledge about the mechanism and causes of AP.

Nursing Protocol Training

Nursing education and training on the protocol were essential to the success of the implementation of the APNP. It was essential for unit leadership to ensure that 100% of their nurses were trained on the appropriate use of the APNP, whereas any missed training opportunities could have negatively impacted patient outcomes and outcome data. As in O'Malley et al. (2018) study, each unit had nurse APNP champions who were provided protected time to assist in APNP adherence and on-the-spot training, as needed, to the nurses. Although no formal data were collected on the amount of time spent by the unit-based champions, valuable antidotal information was shared during the project timeframe. For example, the unit-based champions were instrumental in informing the project author of any trends that suggested

deviation from the protocol implementation—the heightened awareness provided for an increase in perceived nurse autonomy.

For example, in the 91-year-old African American patient who was admitted on November 17, 2020, the nurse evaluated the patient as a poor historian with generalized weakness and moderate musculoskeletal wasting. With these findings in mind, the nurse ordered a speech and language pathology swallow study for which the patient failed, and the nurse implemented the APNP – even though the patient did not meet eligibility criteria. This was an important discovery about nurse buy-in and acceptance of the APNP. Considering the project hospital's younger nurse workforce with an average age ranging from 35 to 44, this nurse's response suggested to the project author that nurses may have felt a sense of empowerment to critically think through complex issues and act autonomously as they deem necessary.

Baseline and Post-intervention Incidence of Aspiration Pneumonia

The implicit research question was whether specialized training of nurses, who care for acutely ill patients at high risk for AP, about AP's pathophysiology, its precipitating factors and adherence to an APNP protocol, will reduce the incidence of AP in designated hospital units. The rationale used for the training of frontline nurses and the strict protocol implementation was based on Cohen's (2018) lean methodology conceptual framework for solving organizational problems that use the Plan, Do, Study and Act (PDSA) approach. This theoretical construct produces a "cultural transformation that alters how a healthcare organization operates...it demands new skills, new habits, and a new attitude throughout the organization from leadership to frontline providers" (p. 1452). A new approach to patient care through Lean methodologies can strengthen an organization's attention to implementing best evidence-based practices and the care delivered to patients.

The results demonstrated the effectiveness of the APNP in reducing the incidence of AP when comparing the preintervention and postintervention data. While the results were not statistically significant, they are clinically significant, with the incidence decreasing from nine to two APs post-intervention. The finding of a decreased AP incidence was consistent with research studies noted in the project author's review of the literature section. As recorded by Altman (2011), Echevarria and Schwoebel (2012), Engvall et al. (2014), O'Malley et al. (2018), and Rosenfeld and Schiffman (2009), identifying a specific patient population with unique comorbidities/characteristics associated with AP and providing a targeted intervention, such as the APNP used in this study, will result in a reduced incidence of this significant diagnosis.

Implications

Due to the limitation of the small sample size, implications and generalizations from the study must be made cautiously. One of the possible implications of this study is that AP is essentially a preventable medical condition. Thus, the nursing staff play a vital role in the monitoring and prevention of the AP. To prevent AP, nurses need to be knowledgeable about AP and be committed to the meticulous implementation of the AP prevention protocol. Another implication of the study deals with the fact that knowledge and nurses training may have created for nurses a heightened sense of autonomy initiating consults and protocols and improved their critical thinking skills, each of which could result in nurses expediting interventions that decrease LOS and promote quality of life. The project findings supported that having a standardized nursing process that identified patients with known AP vulnerabilities decreased the incidences of AP and the APNP served as a critical tool to empower nurses to initiate preventive practices.

Although data were not collected on the LOS associated with AP events during this project, the reduction in AP cases during the project could be viewed as a significant cost saving

from expenditures related to AP in prior years. As demonstrated by Hays et al. (2002), Kaizen et al. (2003), Robinson et al. (2015), Warren et al. (2019) and Wu et al. (2017), a hospital-acquired AP can add a staggering \$40,000 to the cost of treating a patient with AP. Using these data, it is suggested that the project hospital would have experienced cost-avoidance by as much as \$280,000 with seven fewer hospital-acquired APs during the project implementation timeframe. Also noteworthy are the unanticipated costs associated with AP, that is, patients' physical and emotional pain. Patients may experience isolation from their families due to the increased LOS, social and spiritual pain, accompanied by feelings of hopelessness and depression by as much as 20% and 50%, and failure to thrive, as suggested by the literature (Tecuta et al., 2015). An increase of the hospitalization stays by as much as seven to 10 days can compound these adverse outcomes and may slow both physical and spiritual healing.

Limitations

One of the study's major limitations was the limited five-month period of the study. Continued data collections with evaluations of APNP effectiveness may permit broader generalization of the findings to other healthcare systems within the project hospital's network of eight major medical centers that span three states. Another limitation to the study existed mainly because of the global COVID-19 pandemic effects on the healthcare system. The global COVID-19 pandemic required the project hospital's executive leadership to follow the Centers for Disease Control's recommendations to limit hospitalizations, elective surgical cases and outpatient procedures (diagnostics), and all non-critical care admissions, when appropriate. Locally, this decision was made in early April 2020. Subsequently, only patients who were considered critically ill were admitted to the project hospital, which could have influenced the project's outcome data.

The COVID-19 pandemic also had an impact on the availability of staff to care for patients. These limitations resulted in a 34% decrease in hospital admissions, limiting the number of patients meeting eligibility for APNP implementation. This dramatically lowered the project author's ability to demonstrate statistical significance through data. The COVID-19 pandemic surges stressed the facility's staffing methodology and staff were often displaced outside their specialty or parent work units. A small number of staff were afraid of the vulnerabilities of being on COVID-19 – dedicated units and others opted to take a leave of absence. Upwards of 100 hospital staff fell victim to COVID-19 and were placed on quarantine, thus, unavailable to work. Early, during the first surge, the hospital hired over 100 full time employees as "not to exceed" supplemental staff to offset the loss of full time employees unavailable for work. A new staffing model that provided adequate nurse/patient ratios was quickly adopted; however, many of the staff were new to the facility and required expedited hospital orientations that included the APNP, which may have led to traditional processes having varied levels of procedural adherence and changes in practices.

Recommendations for Future Studies

A larger sample size of patients placed on the APNP over a more extended period would allow for more rigor and reliability of interventions and patient outcomes. Additionally, the use of the APNP in other settings, such as long-term acute care settings, community living centers, and home-based primary care, may prevent patients in these settings from acquiring AP that requires hospitalization. Findings from a more extensive study can be presented and results disseminated via national nursing conferences and locally at staff meetings or in-service nursing educational conferences.

Summary and Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to develop and evaluate the effectiveness of a comprehensive APNP to reduce the incidence of AP in patients admitted to a major tertiary Veterans Administration hospital in Southern California. Both retrospective and prospective data on the incidence of hospital-acquired AP were collected to establish baseline data (retrospective) and determine the effectiveness of the APNP (prospective). Information about the number of admissions into patient care units of interest was collected to compare pre-and post-intervention admission rates. Data on demographics of patients with hospital-acquired AP, nurses' AP knowledge level, and nursing compliance (reliability) in implementing the APNP were also collected and analyzed. Patient characteristics related to high-risk comorbidities for AP were identified based upon the review of the literature. Patients admitted to the project setting units who had these high-risk co-morbid conditions became the subject population for the APNP. High-risk AP categories evaluated during this DNP project were neurological disorders, recent intubation, history of head and neck cancer, and oral mucositis. The AP incidence was recorded during the calendar years 2018, 2019, 2020, and January, February, and March 2021.

This time period was necessary as the project author selected the months of November through March for data collection, which encompasses two different calendar years; however, analyses and observations were specific to the timeframes from November through March of each year. Results showed the implementation of a comprehensive AP prevention protocol reduced the incidence of AP from a baseline of seven in the same corresponding five-month period before the AFNP implementation to two events in the same five-month post-implementation timeframe. Even though it was not statistically significant, the downward trend was in the right direction and was clinically significant.

In conclusion, AP is a preventable medical condition. Nurses' level of knowledge, training, and commitment to following the AP prevention protocol were significant factors that resulted in a clinically significant reduction in the incidence of AP.

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APPENDIX A**Institutional Approval Letter**

25 April 2020

This letter is to show that, I, Walt C. Dannenberg, as the Director of the VA Long Beach Healthcare System, give permission to Cory Ramsey to conduct the project titled Implementation of a Nurse-Driven Protocol to Decrease the Incidence of Aspiration Pneumonia (AP) in the Acute Care Setting on the following units: Critical Care Unit, South 10, South 8, North 4, and the Direct Observation Unit.

Upon obtaining all necessary clearances from the Nursing Research Council at the VA Long Beach Healthcare System, and after obtaining the necessary IRB determination/approval, the above-named project lead is allowed to:

1. Collect data regarding the incidence of AP. This will include conducting audits of the electronic medical record (EMR) and looking for patients that have been diagnosed with AP during their inpatient hospital stay.
2. Access to the EMR will be necessary, but patient identifiers will not be recorded.
3. Conduct necessary interactions with staff relevant to their project

The project lead is responsible for ensuring that all activities related to conducting the project are in compliance with the policies that govern practice, HIPPA, and research and research-related regulations at the VA Long Beach Healthcare System and its covered entities.

If you have any questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Signature:

Name: Walt C. Dannenberg

Title: Medical Center Director

Contact Information: 562-826-5402

APPENDIX B

Demographic Data Sheet

Demographic Data Sheet	
Patient Identifier (initial of last name and last four SSN)	
Medical Diagnosis:	
Comorbidities:	
Patient Age:	
Gender:	<input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female
Marital Status:	<input type="checkbox"/> Single <input type="checkbox"/> Married <input type="checkbox"/> Divorced/Separated <input type="checkbox"/> Widowed
Education Level:	<input type="checkbox"/> Elementary School <input type="checkbox"/> High School <input type="checkbox"/> College Degree <input type="checkbox"/> Graduate Degree
Length of Stay in Hospital:	
Type of Diet Prescribed:	<input type="checkbox"/> Regular <input type="checkbox"/> Soft <input type="checkbox"/> Liquid <input type="checkbox"/> Other/Specify:

APPENDIX C

Aspiration Pneumonia Nurse Competency

DEPARTMENT OF VETERANS AFFAIRS MEDICAL CENTER

Name:		Unit:				Date:		
Competency Level Codes				Assessment Methods				
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Little or no experience 2. Needs practice or assistance 3. Competent, performs independently 4. Competent, performs independently and is able to assess others 				<ol style="list-style-type: none"> A. Verbalizes policy, procedure or standard B. Direct Observation/Medical Record C. Demonstration/Return Demonstration D. Certification/Skills Lab/Post Test E. Evaluation of a Mock drill, event or survey F. Other 				
COMPETENCY STATEMENT								
This evaluation tool will be utilized to provide an objective assessment of the individual's ability to verbalize, demonstrate knowledge and competency in all aspects of								
Assessment	Yes or No	Competency Level				Assessment Methods	Initial(s) and Date	Date and Re-evaluation of Competency Level for previous score of 1 or 2
1. Diagnoses:								
a. History of dementia?								
b. Cerebrovascular Accident?								
c. Post-extubation?								
d. Post-procedural sedation?								
e. History of head and neck cancer?								
f. History of diabetes mellitus?								
g. History of neurologic disorder or dysphagia?								
2. Speech Pathology Consultation*								
3. Presence of Feeding Tube:								
a. Head of Bed 30-45 degrees								
b. Verification of feeding tube placement*								
c. Feeding tube anchored correctly*								
d. Check gastric residuals								
e. Perform oral care								
4. Feeding Assessment (No Feeding Tube)								
a. Head of Bed 30-45 degrees								
b. Swallow test								
c. Assessment of alertness:								
1. Person								
2. Place								
3. Time								
d. Oxygen Saturation*								
e. Chewing ability*								
f. Strong gag reflex/cough reflect								
g. Normal annunciation during oral intake								
h. Oral care (halitosis, dry mouth, oral pain, loose teeth)*								
5. Respiratory Compromised Patients: Post-Intubation								
a. Level of consciousness*								
1. Alert to person								
2. Alert to place								
3. Alert to time								
b. Presence of enteral feedings								
c. Delayed gastric emptying								
1. Greater than 90ml of gastric contents*								
2. Presence or absence of gastric bowel sounds*								

3. Complaints of indigestion								
d. Intolerance to HOB at 30-45 degrees								

Competency Level Codes	Assessment Methods
5. Little or no experience 6. Needs practice or assistance 7. Competent, performs independently 8. Competent, performs independently and is able to assess others	G. Verbalizes policy, procedure or standard H. Direct Observation/Medical Record I. Demonstration/Return Demonstration J. Certification/Skills Lab/Post Test K. Evaluation of a Mock drill, event or survey L. Other

COMPETENCY STATEMENT

This evaluation tool will be utilized to provide an objective assessment of the individual's ability to verbalize, demonstrate knowledge and competency in all aspects of

Assessment	Yes or No	Competency Level				Assessment Methods	Initial(s) and Date	Date and Re-evaluation of Competency Level for previous score of 1 or 2
		1	2	3	4			
6. Implementation:								
a. Issue Incentive Spirometer and educate*								
b. Elevate HOB 30-45 degrees*								
c. Develop comprehensive oral care plan*								
d. Obtain order for PPI (when appropriate)								
e. Provide feeding assistance*								
f. Provide pneumonia vaccination (when applicable)								
7. Patient observations during critical time periods (post-admission, snack and meal times):								
a. Elevate HOB 30-45 degrees								
b. Swallow test								
c. Assessment of alertness								
d. Assess oxygen saturation								
e. Assess chewing ability								
f. Assess gag and cough reflex*								
g. Assess annunciation during oral intake								
h. Oral care before and after oral intake*								
8. Sleep time assessment and intervention								
a. Elevate HOB 30-45 degrees*								
b. Assessment of alertness								
1. Person								
2. Place								
3. Time								
c. Call light within reach*								

* denotes Pass/Fail

Comments:

Employee:		Date:
Evaluator:	Initials:	Date:

APPENDIX D

University Institutional Review Board Approval

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH

OFFICE OF RESEARCH & SPONSORED PROGRAMS

DATE: November 2, 2020

TO: Cory Ramsey
FROM: CSULB IRB

PROJECT TITLE: [1657725-1] A COMPREHENSIVE NURSE-DRIVEN PROTOCOL TO DECREASE THE INCIDENCE OF ASPRIATION PNEUMONIA IN AN INTENSIVE CARE UNIT AND MEDICAL/SURGICAL ACUTE CARE SETTINGS

REFERENCE #: 21-067
SUBMISSION TYPE: New Project
REVIEW TYPE: Exempt Review

ACTION: APPROVED under 45 CFR 46 Exempt 104(D)(3).
APPROVAL DATE: November 2, 2020

This is to advise you that the Institutional Review Board for the Protection of Human Subjects (IRB) of California State University, Long Beach, has reviewed your protocol application.

Approval is effective beginning November 2, 2020 and conditional upon your willingness to carry out your continuing responsibilities under University policy:

1. If you need to make changes/revisions to this approved project, you must submit a Request for Amendment to an Approved Protocol form in addition to any documents affected by the requested change. Submit these documents as a subsequent package to your approved project in IRBNet. You are not allowed to implement any changes to your research activities prior to obtaining final approval of your Amendment from the CSULB IRB.
2. You are required to inform the Director of Research Integrity and Compliance, Office of Research & Sponsored Programs, via email at ORSPCompliance within twenty-four hours of any adverse event in the conduct of research involving human subjects. The report shall include the nature of the adverse event, the names of the persons affected, the extent of the injury or breach of confidentiality or data security, if any, and any other information material to the situation.
3. Maintain your research records as detailed in the protocol.

Should you have any questions about the conduct of your research under this protocol, particularly about providing informed consent and unexpected contingencies, please do not hesitate to call the Office of Research & Sponsored Programs at (562) 985-8147. We wish you the best of success in your research.

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board's records.

1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840
Ph. (562) 985-8147 Fax. (562) 985-8665

APPENDIX E

Facility Institutional Review Board Approval

Department of Veterans Affairs	VA Long Beach Healthcare System Research vs. Non-Research Operations Evaluation
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Instructions: In accordance with VHA Program Guide 1200.21, "VHA Operations Activities That May Constitute Research," VALBHS employees may conduct certain operations activities which may or may not constitute research. Whenever the research versus non-research status of an operations activity may be in question, a determination of the status must be made.

Please submit this form to the VALBHS IRB Office by sending a PDF copy with electronic signature to vhalonirb@va.gov. Please reference the VHA Operations Activities that May Constitute Research decision tree for an overview of how a decision between research and non-research activities is determined.

Project Title:	Implementation of a Nurse-Driven Protocol to Reduce the Incidence of Aspiration Pneumonia in the Acute Care Setting.
Project Contact Name:	Cory Ramsey, MHA, RN, NEA-BC Associate Director for Patient Care Services
Email/Phone:	562-826-5402
Department/Service:	Office of the Director

CONDITIONS TO BE CONSIDERED FOR DETERMINATION OF RESEARCH VS. NON-RESEARCH OPERATIONS *NOTE: For answers that are marked "false," you must provide an explanation on page 3.	TRUE	FALSE*
1) The project is designed and/or implemented for internal VA purposes in support of the VA mission(s).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2) The findings are designed to be used by and within VA (or by entities responsible for overseeing VA).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3) Will the activity's findings specifically and exclusively target VA Programs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4) The <u>intent</u> of the project is to improve a process, commonly referred to as quality improvement.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5) The project was NOT designed for the purpose of contributing to generalizable knowledge. <i>See definitions for more detailed information and clarification.</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6) The project is NOT designed to produce information that expands the knowledge base of a scientific discipline (or another scholarly field). <i>See definitions for more detailed information and clarification.</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7) The project is NOT funded or otherwise supported as research by the Office of Research and Development (ORD) or any other sponsor.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8) The project does NOT involve the administration, dispensing and/or use of any drugs, devices and/or biologics?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9) The project does NOT involve design characteristics typically reflective of research, e.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Double-blind interventions • Use of placebo controls • Prospective patient-level randomization to clinical interventions not tailored to individual benefit 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
10) The research does NOT involve the use of biospecimens?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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11) The proposal includes provisions to ensure that the safety, rights, and welfare of patients and staff are appropriately protected as applicable.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
12) The project is NOT intended to meet the requirements set forth by a master's program (or other university level degree program) that requires "research" be conducted.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
13) The activity will NOT be supplemented or modified before, during, or after implementation in order to produce information to expand the knowledge base of a scientific discipline or scholarly field of study or otherwise contribute to generalizable knowledge.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

PROJECT SUMMARY

Reason for Project Locally initiated Mandated by

In the following fields, please provide enough information about the proposed project that a reviewer understands why and how the work will be performed. Please define all acronyms. Failure to address the following will delay determination of your project.

1. Objectives(s): *What is the purpose of the project? What are the issues/questions being addressed and why?*

The purpose of this quality improvement project is to develop and implement a nurse-driven protocol and analyze its effect on the incidence of AP in a veteran population on a medical-surgical unit. The majority of pneumonia diagnosis at the VA Long Beach Healthcare System are associated with the introduction of bacteria from the oral-pharyngeal cavity or the gastrointestinal tract into the lungs where pathogenic bacteria colonize causes AP. AP is often diagnosed in the elderly population and in specific patient groups who suffer from conditions that increase their risk for AP such as patients with neurological disorders, head and neck cancer, and patients who require ventilators. This patient population mirrors what is being discovered at VA Long Beach Healthcare System and we are seeing similar trends.

2. Activities: *Describe what data will be accessed? How will the work be conducted and where? Who will be involved/ have access to the data? Please be detailed in how the work will be conducted including data collection and analysis.*

The project hospital's electronic medical record (EMR) will be used to perform a one-year retrospective chart review to establish the baseline data for hospital-acquired AP diagnoses. One-year of retrospective data is required in order to evaluate the propensity of seasonal-related diagnoses of AP. This is important because seasonal respiratory complications, such as asthma, may predicate complications in breathing and swallowing. Bi-weekly reviews of the EMR will be conducted to determine which patients, if any, have acquired an AP diagnosis. This information will be recorded on the visual management process control board and the data will be discussed at the daily huddle for a period of four months. Daily huddle will allow for near real-time rapid improvements in the event it is determined the protocol requires modification(s). The outcomes will be discussed weekly at the TPOC review of measures with executive leadership where resource support will be allocated when necessary. Exclusionary criteria will be observed. An AP rate will be calculated based upon the total sample size and the bed days of care of all patients between the months of December 2020 and April 2021. Results will be displayed on the process control boards, as well as, the project hospital's TPOC visual management briefing zone. Outcomes will be plotted using run charts and will be displayed using time sequencing and trend lines will be utilized to allow for rapid interpretations. A red or green andon placed in the top left-hand corner of the run chart will indicate whether the project is poised to meet its goals (red – not on track; green – on track). Key stakeholders in the PI event include the patients and their families because the interventions that are put in place are expected to benefit the patients' health outcomes. The nursing staff will be

largely responsible for adhering to the protocol and evaluating its effectiveness. Hospital administrators, who will be engaged with the PI from the beginning, will also be interested in the outcomes of the protocol because it is anticipated that average LOS will be lowered which can decrease costs. Hospital administrators will also ensure the taskforce has adequate resources (e.g., time, financials, and equipment) allocated in order for the PI event to yield the greatest results. Provider staff are also important stakeholders that will be involved throughout the PI event. In order to gain their confidence, they will need to be involved from the development of the protocol through its full implementation. The nurse informaticist will be instrumental in ensuring the data is reliable and for making the necessary modifications to the EMR. Other key stakeholders include the PI taskforce, QSV, hospital education staff, and unit-based managers. The author will collaborate with a speech and language pathologist and the project hospital's Designated Learning Officer to provide one-on-one training for nurse champions. For the remainder of the staff, the nurse-driven protocol will be conducted onsite of the project hospital and will encompass teaching strategies devised by the individual unit nurse educators, nurse champions, and the facility's Designated Learning Officer (DLO). The education sessions will take place three times daily for 5 days or longer, if needed. Each nurse will receive a didactic training session aimed at refamiliarizing the nurse to the physiology of swallowing and the conditions that place a patient at greatest risk for AP. Hands-on learning with one-on-one observations of the nurses implementing the protocol will also be a portion of the training. The nurses' competencies will be assessed at the conclusion of the training sessions utilizing the project hospital's standardized competency tool. The tool permits the trainers to rate the nurses' protocol demonstration as performing to the level of "Can Teach Others", "Performs Independently", or "Needs Improvement".

3. Impact/Significance: *What will be done with the resulting information? Will the activity*

Through patient chart reviews that will be conducted by the process owner, the incidence of AP will be estimated and a rate will be calculated using the total number of inpatients (numerator) divided by the number of patients who have been diagnosed with a hospital-acquired AP (denominator). These data will be recorded on a run chart and updated daily at the process control board prior to the daily meetings. Outcome data will be stored in a secure online folder within the project hospital's internet network and will be password protected.

Provide an explanation below for responses marked "false" on page 1 or 2.
Please number your responses to indicate the question (#1-12) you are addressing.

[Empty rectangular box for content]

By signing this document, the signer affirms that the information in the statements above is the truth to the best of their knowledge at this time. The signer is aware that should this project/ operation be modified they will need to re-submit so a review and determination of the modification can be completed to ensure the original determination is not changed.

Signature of Responsible Project Lead: Greg Kamary Date: 5/5/2020

Department of Veterans Affairs

VA Long Beach Healthcare System
Research vs. Non-Research Operations Evaluation

FOR VALBHS RESEARCH OFFICE USE ONLY BELOW THIS LINE

Not Research. VALBHS has determined that based on the responses above and the proposed project description approval by an IRB or other review committee is not needed. The project is considered to be non-research VHA operations activity. If the results of this project are presented or published they cannot be presented as research, nor does it have research approval.

- Any change made before, during, or after implementation that results in an intent to expand the knowledge base of a scientific discipline or scholarly field of study, or otherwise contribute to generalizable knowledge, constitutes research and must be submitted to an IRB or other pertinent review committee.
- Please note it is the responsibility of this individual and/or each VA author and coauthor (in cases of publication) to retain a copy of this form for a minimum of 6 years after publication and in accordance with any applicable records retention schedules. A copy of this review document will also be retained by Research Service.
- Publications or presentations of findings from Non-Research activities should be documented, prior to publication or presentation by the project lead to the Facility Director or other individual designated in writing by the Facility Director. (Sample document provided in this form)

Research. As designed, this project requires review by an IRB or other appropriate review committee *prior* to initiation. Please contact the Research Office for more information.

Additional information is needed to make a determination. See comments below.

Reviewer Comments:

Reviewer Signature: Maria Rodriguez

Date: 5/5/2020

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DEFINITIONS

VHA Program Guide 1200.21: VHA Operations Activities That May Constitute Research

a. **Generalizable Knowledge.** Generalizable knowledge is information that expands the knowledge base of a scientific discipline or other scholarly field of study. Systematic investigations designed to develop or contribute to generalizable knowledge constitute research.

NOTE: Quality Improvement / Quality Assurance activities occur all the time to ensure quality care is provided and sometimes the analysis of the data for these activities may lead to information that expands the knowledge base of a scientific discipline or other scholarly field of study. However, it is the original intent of the project that is used in this determination. That is, if the original quality improvement/assurance activity was designed with the intention to expand on new scientific knowledge, then this would be considered research.

b. **Operations Activities.** Operations activities are administrative, financial, legal, quality assurance, quality improvement, and public health endeavors that are necessary to support VHA's missions of delivering health care to the Nation's Veterans, performing medical education, and contributing to national emergency response. Operations activities may or may not constitute research.

c. **Research.** Research is a systematic investigation (including research development, testing, and evaluation) designed to develop or contribute to generalizable knowledge. Given the definition of generalizable knowledge in subparagraph 3a, research may also be defined as a systematic investigation designed to produce information to expand the knowledge base of a scientific discipline (or other scholarly field of study).

d. **Systematic Investigation.** A systematic investigation is an activity that is planned in advance and that uses data collection and analysis to answer a question. Although research must include systematic investigation, non-research operations activities also include systematic investigation to ensure reliable outcomes. Systematic investigation does not, in and of itself, define research.

EXAMPLES

Projects may be systematic but not "research." Some examples of activities that are not "research" include:

Quality improvement or assurance (QI/QA) projects:

- QI/QA projects are designed to continuously improve the quality or performance of a department or program where it is not the intention to share the results beyond the hospital.
- QI projects are designed and implemented for internal VA purposes; and
- QI projects are not designed to produce information that expands the knowledge base of a scientific discipline (or other scholarly field)

Other Examples of VA activities that typically do not constitute research:

- Patient satisfaction surveys
- Evaluation activities related to policy development
- Employee performance evaluation activities
- Regulatory compliance activities

- Medication use evaluations
- Scholarly and journalistic activities
- Public health surveillance activities
- Criminal Justice or criminal investigative biospecimens/records
- US intelligence, homeland security, defense, or other national security missions

SAMPLE FORMAT (Add to VA Letterhead)

Documentation of Non-Research Activities For Publications Outside the VA

Title of Proposed Publication:

As an author of the publication referenced above (copy attached), I attest that the findings reported in the publication were not derived, in whole or in part, from activities constituting research as described in VHA Program Guide 1200.21. The project generating these findings was conceived and conducted as a non-research operations activity involving [PROJECT DESCRIPTION].

(Provide the following for each VA author.)

Lead Author Signature:

Date:

Lead Author Name:

VA Duty Station:

Co-Author Signature:

Date:

Co-Author Name:

VA Duty Station:

[ADD ADDITIONAL CO-AUTHORS' INFORMATION AS RELEVANT]

Attestation of Designated Official

As the Director or Director-designated representative of the VA Long Beach Healthcare System, I have reviewed the publication and author attestation(s), and attest that findings reported in the publication did not arise from activities that constituted research as described in VHA Program Guide 1200.21.

Signature of Designated Official:

Date:

Name:

Title: